

Comparative Study of Self Esteem and Family Environment among College Students belonging to Rural and Urban Locality

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Abstract

The present study has been undertaken to study the self-esteem and family environment among college students. The present study was based on the sample of 200 college students. The researcher has used simple random sampling for the selection of students and collection of data. The researcher in the present study has used standardized scale developed by Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) and standardized family environment scale developed by the Bhatia and Chadha. The collected data has been analyzed with the help of critical ratio. After the analysis of data, it has been found that there is significant difference in the self-esteem of college students belonging to different locality (rural and urban). Significant difference was also found in the family environment of college students belonging to different locality (rural and urban).

Keywords: - *Self-esteem, family environment, college students, rural and urban locality.*

INTRODUCTION

Self-esteem is an insight of an individual's significance or value, as well as the degree to which that significance or value is accepted or recognized. Self-esteem is a basic human

necessity because it is very much required for inspiration. It improves a person's self-confidence by promoting a positive sense of self and optimistic attitude. Self-esteem can be both great and low. People with high self-esteem

enjoy participating in a variety of activities in their daily lives.

They are filled with optimism and zeal. They are working to solve their problems. As a result, they are willing to change and accept themselves as they are, and they have no inferiority complex. People with low self-esteem, on the other side, are jealous, lack confidence, do not trust in themselves, and are unwilling to change. Teenage years is a time of life when one's sense of self undergoes significant changes. The child's first school is his or her family. The family is the social agency that helps a child to develop social skills. A teenager learns to deal with emotions and drives in a socially acceptable manner in his or her family. Adolescents have been affected by changes in family structure and surroundings. The family is where a child's self-esteem is formed. The family plays a very important role in the growth and development of the individual.

Several studies have been conducted on self-esteem and family environment at college and university level, ([Bansal, 2016](#)) has explored the correlation between the family environment and self-esteem of adolescents. The results of the study revealed that there is positive correlation between self-esteem and family environment of adolescents. ([Amalu, 2017](#)) has studied the family environment and self-esteem of

secondary school students. The results of the study revealed that positive family cohesion, support and less family conflicts were the significant predictors of psychological adjustment. ([Aggarwal, 2021](#)) has studied the effect of family environment on self-esteem of adolescents in relation to their socioeconomic status and found that cohesion, expressiveness and independence dimensions of family environment have fundamental impact on the adolescents' self-esteem. ([Cheema and Bharadwaj, 2021](#)) has studied the self-esteem and academic achievement in relation to home environment among adolescents and explored that favorable home environment has positive influence on self-esteem and vice versa.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The present education system is learner centered, and its main aim is all round development of the learners i.e., Physical, mental, social, emotional, spiritual, aesthetic. In the modern time, this study has great significance because it throws light on the self-esteem and family environment of college students. This study proves helpful in making the students aware of self-esteem and family environment. The finding of the study also enables the teachers and parents to know about the self-esteem and family environment of

college students belonging to different locality (rural and urban). The findings of this study also help the teachers and parents and society at large to know the difference in self-esteem and family environment of college students belonging to different locality. With the help of findings of the present study both parents and teacher should be able to know that self-esteem and family environment had greater impact on academic achievement of the students and overall growth and development of the child. Both teachers and parents should try to create the supportive emotional environment so that adolescents do not feel alone, helpless and unwanted in home as well as in schools. All the members of society should try to understand the self-esteem of the students and keeping into consideration their family environment and treat them accordingly.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The researchers have reviewed several studies and found that very less studies have been conducted in Jammu on self-esteem and family environment of college students. Thus, the researcher has selected the study as under

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)
2. To study the difference in family environment of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)
2. There is no significant difference in family environment of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. This study was confined to Jammu only.
2. This study was confined to colleges of Jammu only.
3. This study was confined to sample of 200 (100 boys and 100 girls) college students only.

METHODOLOGY: In the present study the researcher has used the descriptive survey method.

POPULATION: All the college students (Male and Female) studying in 1st and third year of B.A/B.SC/B.COM course belonging to different

locality constitute population for the present study.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE USED: The researcher has applied simple random sampling technique for the selection of sample.

SAMPLE: The sample of the present study consist of 200 students (100 boys and 100 girls) selected from the colleges of Jammu.

TOOL USED: In the present study the researcher has used standardized Rosenberg Self-Esteem

Scale (RSES) and standardized family environment scale developed by the Bhatia and Chadha.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA: The collected data for any research purpose has no meaning until and unless the collected data analyzed with the help of appropriate statistical technique. In the present study the researcher has applied Mean, Standard deviation and critical ratio as a statistical technique for data analysis.

Table 4.1 Showing critical ratio for difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)

Locality	Mean	S. D	N	SEM	SEDM	C.R.	Level of significance
Rural	37.22	6.38	100	0.63	0.81	4.30	Significant
Urban	40.71	4.99	100	0.49			

*Significant at .05 level

**Significant at .01 level

The table 4.1 and fig 1 indicates that the critical ratio for difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban) came out to be 4.30 whereas table value is 1.96 at .05 level of significance and 2.58 at .01 level of significance. Hence the obtained value was found to be significant. Therefore, on the basis of the value obtained the researcher could interpret that there is difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and

urban). Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is rejected which states that there is no significant difference in self-esteem of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban). Obtained mean value of urban college students came out to be 40.71 is higher than the mean value of rural college students i.e., 37.22, which clearly states that urban college students have better self-esteem than the rural college students.

Table 4.2 Showing critical ratio for difference in family environment of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban)

Locality	Mean	S. D	N	SEM	SEDM	C.R.	Level of significance

Rural	273.26	40.26	100	4.02	5.22	3.19	Significant
Urban	289.94	33.22	100	3.32			
*Significant		at		.05		level	

FAMILY ENVIRONMENT MEAN AND S.D OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

■ RURAL ■ URBAN

**Significant at .01 level

The table 4.2 and fig 2 indicates that the critical ratio for difference in family environment of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban) came out to be 3.19 whereas table value is 1.96 at .05 level of significance and 2.58 at .01 level of significance. Hence the obtained value was found to be significant. Therefore, on the basis of the value obtained the researcher could interpret that there is difference in family environment of college students in terms of

locality (rural and urban). Therefore, Hypothesis 2 is rejected which states that there is no significant difference in family environment of college students in terms of locality (rural and urban). Obtained mean value of urban college students came out to be 289.94 is higher than the mean value of rural college students i.e., 273.26, which clearly states that urban college students have better family environment than the rural college students.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the present study revealed that there is significant difference in self-esteem of college students belonging to different locality (rural and urban). The results of the present study also revealed that there is significant difference in the family environment of college students belonging to rural and urban locality.

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